

Incidence of AKI after burn injury in pediatric population

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine the overall incidence of acute kidney injury (AKI), risk factors for AKI, and the influence of AKI on outcome in pediatric burn patients. Additionally, the modified pediatric criteria for the severity of acute kidney injury (AKI) were applied to these patients. All consecutive patients admitted between June 2016 and May 2018 who were diagnosed with a burn injury that affected 10 percent or more of their total body surface area as a percentage (TBSA, percent) (a 2-year period). The information from 123 different patients was analyzed. It was shown that 45.5 percent of patients had AKI. Patients who were diagnosed with AKI were more likely to pass away than those who did not have AKI ($p = 0.057$). The combination of serum creatinine and urine output criteria determined that all of the patients who did not survive had pRIFLE AKI. Patients who were diagnosed with a more severe type of AKI (Failure and Injury) as well as patients who were diagnosed with late AKI had a greater number of episodes of sepsis in comparison to patients who were diagnosed with early AKI and the Risk category of AKI. According to the findings of a logistic regression analysis, the presence of sepsis and septic shock as well as the PRISM score and TBSA were independent risk factors for the Failure class of acute renal injury in pediatric burn patients. Within the burn population, we noticed a somewhat significant prevalence of AKI. There is some evidence that sepsis has a role in the progression of AKI to the Failure class. A high risk of death is connected with having an AKI class of maximum failure.

Keywords: Critically ill children, Burn, Acute kidney injury, Sepsis, Septic shock

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Introduction

Acute kidney injury (also known as AKI) is a common complication that occurs in burn patients who are hospitalized to the intensive care unit (ICU), although the incidence rates vary depending on the burn population that was studied

and the AKI definition that was employed [1, 2]. The Risk, Injury, Failure, Loss of kidney function, and End-stage kidney disease (RIFLE) [3], the Acute Kidney Injury Network (AKIN) [4], and the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) criteria [5] are the consensus definitions of AKI that have been developed to include all severity levels of AKI and to allow comparisons between studies.

In burn patients, a number of risk factors for AKI have been discovered. These risk factors include a high age, the size and/or cause of the burn injury, and the presence of multiple organ failure and/or sepsis [2]. On the other hand, the majority of the results of preventive measures have been underwhelming so far [6]. Acute kidney injury is a diverse illness that can range from a subclinical loss in kidney function to the requirement for renal replacement treatment (RRT). In spite of the formulation of international treatment standards [5], the actual therapy of AKI and the utilization of RRT differ significantly from one region of the world to another [7].

AKI in patients who have suffered burns is linked to a higher risk of death [2, 8], and it probably also contributes to a longer length of stay (LOS) [2]. It has become apparent from research conducted on various patient groups that individuals who have survived AKI are at a higher risk of developing chronic kidney disease (CKD) and have an elevated risk of long-term morbidity and mortality [9]. AKI may also be a burden on the health care system, leading to significantly increased treatment expenses, particularly those costs that are associated to the utilization of RRT [10].

Methods

The Human Subjects Review Board of the Janaki Medical College Teaching Hospital in Janakpur, Nepal gave their approval to conduct this research, and they did not ask the family to provide informed consent. Over the course of two years, in a pediatric burn ICU with seven beds and specialized care and burn unit, a retrospective analysis was carried out. Patients who were consecutively admitted to the care unit at the Janaki Medical College Teaching Hospital in Janakpur and who had a burn injury that affected 10 percent or more of their total body surface area (TBSA) were considered for inclusion in the study. The following were the criteria for excluding patients from the study: nonsurvivable burn (determination to provide comfort treatment upon arrival); admission for a condition other than burn; burn size of less than 10 percent. The written treatment plan that we follow in the intensive care unit served as a guide during the resuscitation of the patient. After the first 48 hours, the maintenance crystalloid infusion rate was estimated using conventional formulas for insensible fluid losses. The resuscitation of fluids was based on the Parkland formula during those first 48 hours. Further changes to the infusion of crystalloid fluid were based on the outcomes of the clinical and laboratory assessments. Early enteral feeding was provided, and no antibiotics were administered for preventative purposes. Within three days of admission, the wounds were cleaned and dressed. The Pediatric Risk of Mortality II (PRISM II) score was used to rate the severity of the patient's illness upon admission to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU). The patient was diagnosed with sepsis using the currently accepted diagnostic criteria, and the diagnosis was documented throughout their stay in the intensive care unit [10, 11]. For each patient, demographic and clinical data were recorded, such as the length of time spent in the intensive care unit and the hospital, the length of time spent on mechanical ventilation, abdominal compartment syndrome, nephrotoxic drugs (such as aminoglycosides and vancomycin), and vasopressors (such as dopamine, epinephrine, and norepinephrine), inhalation or electrical injury. The urinary bladder pressure measurement method was used to determine the intra-abdominal pressure, and the abdominal compartment syndrome (ACS) was defined as a sustained intra-abdominal pressure of more than 20 mmHg that was associated with new organ dysfunction or failure, in accordance with the

recommendations of the International ACS Consensus Definitions Conference [12]. Baseline estimated creatinine clearance (eCCL) was calculated by using the Schwartz equation from a serum creatinine measured within 3 months prior to ICU admission; if this was unavailable, the patients were assigned to a baseline eCCL of 120 ml/min/1.73 m² [13, 14]. This was done in order to compare the patients with those who had a baseline eCCL of 120 ml/min/1.73 m² or higher. Patients were given a classification based on the highest pRIFLE class (class R, class I, or class F) that they reached during their time in the intensive care unit. The pRIFLE class was assigned based on the patient who had the lowest score for either the eCCL or the urine output. Patients were considered to be suffering from acute renal damage if they met any one of the criteria for that categorization in the pRIFLE system. If kidney impairment was identified after 5 postburn days, then the diagnosis of AKI is considered to be late. Mortality rates were recorded in the ICU.

Statistical analysis

Dichotomous and categorical variables were compared using the χ^2 test; comparisons of location parameters for continuous data were analyzed with Mann–Whitney and Kruskal–Wallis tests. Risk factors were assessed with univariate analysis and the variables that were statistically significant in the univariate analysis were included in the multivariate analysis by applying a multiple logistic regression with AKI and Failure class of AKI as the dependent outcome variables. In all comparisons, a *p* value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data are expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD).

Results

Over the course of two years, there were 221 patients who were continuously admitted to the burn ICU. Ninety-eight cases were not included because they did not meet any of the following criteria: burn area less than 10 percent (*n* = 59), admission for a condition other than burn (*n* = 31), a priori choice to withdraw or withhold therapy upon arrival to ICU (*n* = 8). The information gathered from the remaining 123 patients was analyzed.

Only in those four patients for whom the baseline serum creatinine concentration was available was the baseline estimated creatinine clearance (eCCL) determined using the Schwartz equation. The remaining 119 patients were assigned a baseline eCCL of 120 ml/min/1.73 m² as their value.

Table 1 contains information regarding the demographics and clinical characteristics of the patient.

Table 1 : Characteristics of patients with and without AKI

	No acute kidney injury (<i>n</i> = 67)	Acute kidney injury (<i>n</i> = 56)	<i>p</i> value
Age	7.4 $\pm$ 5.4	6.74 $\pm$ 5.4	ns
Gender (% of male)	70%	59%	ns
PRISM on admission	4.5 $\pm$ 3.2	8.7 $\pm$ 6	<0.001
TBSA (%) on admission	22.6 $\pm$ 13	41.7 $\pm$ 17	<0.001
Electrical injury (%)	5.9%	7.1%	ns
Inhalational injury (%)	16.4%	26.7%	ns
Number of surgical procedures	1.3 $\pm$ 1.2	3.7 $\pm$ 2.8	<0.001
Abdominal compartment syndrome (%)	0%	16%	<0.001
Sepsis during ICU stay (%)	19.8%	38.4%	<0.05
Nephrotoxic drugs (%)	25%	32.1%	0.08

	No acute kidney injury (n = 67)	Acute kidney injury (n = 56)	p value
Vasoactive drugs (%)	15.9%	35.7%	<0.05
Length of mechanical ventilation (days)	4.9 ± 6	23.3 ± 27	0.001
Length of ICU stay (days)	12.8 ± 11	36.7 ± 36	0.001
Length of hospital stay (days)	18 ± 13	51 ± 40	0.001
ICU mortality (%)	1.5%	8.9%	0.057

AKI acute kidney injury; TBSA total burn surface area; PRISM Pediatric Risk of Mortality score; ns nonsignificant; continuous variables, mean ± standard deviation (SD); categorical variables, (%)

Of the 56 patients with kidney injury, 37 had early and 19 had late AKI. Eighty-two percent of patients with late AKI had septic episodes compared to 19% of patients with early occurrence of AKI. The mortality rate of patients with early and late AKI was 5.4% (2 patients from 37) and 15.7% (3 patients from 19), respectively, p = 0.19.

Table 2 compares data of patient categories based on their attainment of RIFLE criteria by eCCL only, by urine output only, or by the combination of both.

Table 2: Characteristics of patients with AKI (classification according to type of RIFLE criteria attained)

	UO criteria, n = 9	eCCL n = 32	criteria, Both n = 15	UO + eCCL criteria, n = 15	p value
Age (years)	2.3 ± 0.6	7.4 ± 5.5	6.7 ± 5.4		0.15
TBSA (%)	40 ± 25.9	41 ± 15.2	45.6 ± 21.7		0.65
PRISM	9 ± 4.6	8.7 ± 6.3	7.7 ± 5		0.4
Length of ICU stay (days)	44.3 ± 43.4	39.1 ± 38.3	31.5 ± 37.3		0.38
Length of hospital stay (days)	52.8 ± 49.5	55 ± 47	66.3 ± 56		0.4
Length of mechanical ventilation (days)	34.7 ± 46.3	23.9 ± 28.5	19.3 ± 22.7		0.59
Failure AKI class	0%	12.5%	40%		<0.01
Mortality (%)	0	0	33.3		<0.001

UO urine output; eCCL estimated creatinine clearance; AKI acute kidney injury; TBSA total burn surface area; PRISM Pediatric Risk of Mortality score; continuous variables, mean ± standard deviation (SD); categorical variables, (%)

Table 3: Comparison of characteristics and outcomes of patients with risk, injury, failure classes according to pRIFLE classification

	Risk	Injury	Failure	p value
Number	18 (32%)	28 (50%)	10 (18%)	
Age (years)	8.9 ± 6.1	6.2 ± 5	5.6 ± 4.6	0.48
Gender (% of male)	61.1	87.5	50	0.8
PRISM ^b	6.6 ± 3.7	8.2 ± 5.7	12.1 ± 7.6	0.05
TBSA (%) ^d	40.8 ± 14.9	38.4 ± 18.4	51.9 ± 18.4	0.05
AKI on admission (%)	61	53.6	60	0.15
Surgeries before RIFLE max (number)	1 ± 0.8	0.96 ± 1.5	1.4 ± 0.9	0.13
Surgeries 72 h before RIFLE max (number)	0.94 ± 0.8	0.48 ± 0.7	0.8 ± 0.7	0.09

	Risk	Injury	Failure	p value
Inhalational injury (%) ^a	11.1	28.6	50	0.04
Electrical injury (%) ^a	16.7	3.5	0	0.05
Bilirubin at RIFLE max (mg/dl) ^d	0.8 ± 0.3	0.63 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 1.3	0.006
Platelets at RIFLE max (×10 ⁹ /l) ^c	255 ± 146	199 ± 285	174 ± 56	0.05
pO ₂ /FiO ₂ at RIFLE max	324 ± 96	318.6 ± 90	274 ± 123	0.5
PT > 1.5 of normal at RIFLE max (%) ^a	0	10.7	80	<0.001
PTT > 1.5 of normal at RIFLE max (%) ^a	27.8	35.7	80	0.019
Sepsis at RIFLE max (%) ^a	16.7	32.1	90	<0.001
Septic shock at RIFLE max (%) ^d	16.7	21.4	90	0.001
Nephrotoxic drugs at RIFLE max (%) ^a	11.1	35.7	60	0.04
Vasoactive drugs at RIFLE max (%) ^d	22.2	25	90	<0.001
Abdominal compartment syndrome at RIFLE max (%) ^a	0	17.9	40	0.021
Length of ICU stay (days)	37.2 ± 41.5	35.3 ± 34	41.7 ± 41.2	0.2
Length of hospital stay (days)	44.5 ± 42	45 ± 38	56.3 ± 52	0.3
Length of mechanical ventilation (days)	21.6 ± 26	22.5 ± 30	28.4 ± 23	0.43
Mortality (%) ^d	0	0	50	<0.001

TBSA total burn surface area; PRISM Pediatric Risk of Mortality score; LOS length of stay; PT prothrombin time; PTT partial thromboplastin time; pO₂/FiO₂, arterial oxygen tension (PaO₂)/fractional inspired oxygen (FiO₂) ratio; continuous variables, mean ± standard deviation (SD); categorical variables, (%)

^aRisk versus failure versus injury

^bRisk versus failure

^cRisk versus injury and failure

^dFailure versus risk and injury

Logistic regression analysis indicated that PRISM score (OR 1.3, 95% CI 1.1–1.4; $p = 0.05$) and TBSA (OR 1.04, 95% CI 1.002–1.1; $p < 0.001$) were the independent risk factors for acute kidney injury in pediatric burn patients; the presence of sepsis (OR 3.1, CI 1.2–5.9; $p = 0.05$) and septic shock (OR 2.8, CI 1.1–6.02, $p = 0.02$) were the independent risk factor for the Failure class of AKI.

Plotz et al. [15] found that the incidence of AKI in general pediatric ICU patients was 58 percent. Our study found that the incidence of AKI in pediatric burn patients was 45.5%, which is lower than the 58.5% incidence that they found. The diagnosis of AKI in our patients was predominately based on the eCCL or on both urine output and eCCL criteria, and this was predicated on a combination of urine output and eCCL in all patients who did not survive their illness. Aksan-Arican et al. [6] also observed a greater mortality rate for pediatric patients who obtained AKI by pRIFLE creatinine criteria compared with patients who only attained pRIFLE urine output criteria. This was the case even though both patient groups met the same criteria. In juvenile patients with oliguria and/or anuria and creatinine elevation, aggressive therapeutic measures, such as renal replacement therapy, may lead to an improvement in the survival rate.

It has been demonstrated that severity scores obtained upon admission are helpful tools for predicting the incidence of acute kidney injury (AKI) or the Failure class of AKI [9, 16, 17]. In our study, patients who developed AKI had higher TBSA and PRISM scores on admission. In logistic regression analysis, both the PRISM score and TBSA were factors that increased the likelihood of developing AKI. There was no difference in age, gender, or the existence of inhalational or electrical harm between patients who did and did not have AKI. When compared to patients in the Risk category of AKI, patients in the Injury and Failure classes of AKI have a much higher frequency of inhalational injury. This is an important finding to make note of.

There has been a report of a mortality rate of fifty percent in pediatric patients who had both renal failure and multiorgan failure as a result of sepsis complications [18–20]. When we evaluated patients with different categories of AKI, we found that those with severe AKI (Injury and Failure) were more likely to experience bouts of sepsis and septic shock than those with a Risk category of AKI. It would appear that the presence of sepsis is the risk factor for the Failure class of acute kidney injury (AKI). Patients who acquired AKI after 5 postburn days had a considerably greater frequency of sepsis as well, however in contrast to patients who got AKI early on, these patients did not have a higher fatality rate than patients who had AKI early on.

Although drug-induced renal dysfunction is rather common in critically sick burn patients [9], we did not find any significant differences in the usage of nephrotoxic drugs between patients with acute kidney injury (AKI) and patients who did not have AKI. There was a correlation between the severity of AKI and an increasing use of nephrotoxic and vasoactive medications. This, together with the rises in bilirubin and thrombocytopenia, most likely reflects the severity of the disease and the presence of sepsis.

It is interesting that abdominal compartment syndrome developed in forty percent of patients with the Failure class of AKI. Intra-abdominal hypertension is a risk factor for renal failure [21], and it also has the effect of lowering the systemic hemodynamics and renal function.

Several research [8, 9, 20] have discussed the correlation between acute renal injury and the prognosis of burn victims. According to the findings of our research, patients who had AKI were more likely to pass away than patients who did not have AKI; however, the mortality rate was significantly greater in the Failure category when compared to both the Risk and Injury classes. Previous research addressing the severity of AKI and outcome [16, 23] backs up these findings, which show consistency with those findings.

This study suffers from a number of shortcomings. To begin, this research was only carried out at a single location, and only a limited number of participants participated. Second, because the study was designed to be retrospective and observational, it is impossible to draw any definitive conclusions regarding the causal relationship that exists between AKI and death.

We come to the conclusion that a pRIFLE categorization system can be useful in improving one's understanding of the epidemiology of AKI in pediatric burn patients who are in critical condition. It may be helpful in the design of larger multicenter trials to have information on the overall incidence of acute kidney injury (AKI), risk factors for AKI, and the influence of AKI on outcome in pediatric patients with severe burn injury. These trials are intended to determine the contribution of AKI to patients' morbidity and mortality and to evaluate the effect of early initiation of aggressive measures to both prevent and treat AKI in pediatric burn ICU patients.

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